

Transitional Words in English and Arabic

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: April 13, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: September 13, 2021</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Transitional words, Additive, Causative</p> <hr/> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5504172</p>	<p><i>The current study emphasizes on the notion of transition words which can be considered as both stylistic and syntactic phenomenon. As Quirk et al (1985:634) suggest, conjuncts have seven roles. One of these roles is that transitional role. The problem of this study is that Iraqi EFL learners find difficulties in interpreting some texts. The aim of this study is to investigate similarities and differences of this phenomenon in both Arabic and English for the purpose of solving such problems encountering learners. It is hypothesized that Arabic has more transitional words than English. The data analysis of English is limited to some selected texts of the novel "Wuthering Heights" while in Arabic it is limited to some selected verses of the Holy Quran. It has been observed that Arabic shows more illustration than English language. The value of the current study is that it provides an adequate background knowledge for those who are interested in this domain.</i></p>

Introduction

1.1 Transitional Words: Definitions

Carter (2013: 31) describes transition words, often known as signal words. They are used to link thoughts in a logical progression from one to the other. Transition words are utilized frequently in writing making ideas together and indicating important points. For instances, "like, similarly, in other words, in contrast, on the other hand, but, instead of, consequently, therefore, first, second, and finally".

He (ibid) suggests that definition clues can usually have the unknown word in "bold print or italics", so it represents, like a key word. Normally, transition words or phrases like *means, is defined as, or is followed by* the word you do not know. Definition clues may also be distinguished through punctuation, such as, a colon (:) or a dash (-) followed by the definitions.

Besides, Aten (2008: 92) states that transition words function to connect ideas clearly. These words help make sentences and paragraphs flow together smoothly. For example:

- *It started to rain very hard. We stopped playing baseball.*

These two sentences need something to connect them so that the reader knows that the rain was the reason that the baseball game was stopped. Transition words can make this connection.

He (ibid: 193) adds that transition words or phrases are used to point out and change from one idea to another. Certain transitional words or phrases are used to reflect the sequence or order in which things happen.

Furthermore, Halliday and Hasan (1976: 227) mention that with transitional words, one can move into a different kind of semantic relationships, one which is no longer any type of search constructions, but a specification of the way in which what is to follow is lexically connected to what has gone before.

Royal (2012: 56), in his turn, argues that transition words, such as "but" and "however," have been called the traffic lights of language. They serve one of four primary purposes: to show contrast, illustration, continuation, or conclusion. He (ibid) adds that words of illustration include "first," "second," "for instance," and "for example." "So" signals conclusion. "However" signals contrast. "Moreover" signals continuation:

"Time management involves thinking in terms of effectiveness first and efficiency second. Whereas efficiency is concerned with doing a task in the fastest possible manner, effectiveness is concerned with spending time doing the "right" things. Effectiveness is therefore a broader, more useful concept, which questions whether we should even do a particular task".

Consequently, Lyon (2003: 62) points out that transition words produce smooth reading and contribute to a piece's cohesiveness. If one begins with an anecdotal lead, for instance, his/her transition must be a clear statement of his/her subject or theme. Transitions bring the reader from his/her lead into the rest of his/her piece. In terms of techniques, a single word or phrase may indicate a transition. This transition is the easiest—perhaps not the least visible—ways to shift gears. Words such as "however," "so," "in addition," and "yet" are a few such transition words, (Lyon, 2003: 62).

A typical transition from one phrase and paragraph to another is the introductory independent or dependent clauses. An "independent clause," to review grammar, can "stand on its own." It is "independent" because it contains a subject, verb, and object. The independent clause in the following sentence is italicized:

- Although he had been to Boston as a child, *he was unprepared for the changes he saw.*

A "dependent clause" does not contain all of the parts of a sentence and is thus "dependent" upon the rest of the sentence to be grammatically complete, such as "*In the 1900s, everyone knew how to bake a pie*", (ibid).

1.2 Types of Transitional Words

Sayidina (2010: 256) distinguishes four types of transitional words which can be illustrated as follows:

1.2.1 Additive

Halliday and Matthiessen (2004: 406) claim that additive is simply one process that is adjoined to another. Sayidina (2010: 256), in his turn, maintains that in this type of transition words, prepositions are added to preceding ones. Typical additive transitions include: "*and, also, furthermore, moreover, besides, in addition, for example*", (ibid). Besides, Schiffrin (1987: 33) adds that additive transitional words have both structural roles in the sense that they join two or more structural units together and cohesive roles since the interpretation of the whole utterance is dependent on the relationships between the various pieces of utterance.

1.2.2 Causative

Leech (2006: 17) mentions that adverbials of reason or cause express a link of cause and effect between two ideas, as in clauses introduced by *because, as or since*: *I was sick because I ate too much trifle*. Prepositional phrases of cause or reason are introduced by such prepositions as *because of, on account of*: *He couldn't see her face because of the thick white veil*. The same basic notion can be conveyed by causative verbs such as *angered* in *My refusal angered her*. Other examples of causative verbs are *weaken, beautify, immunize* (derived from the adjectives weak, beautiful, immune).

In this respect, Sayidina (2010: 256) states that in a causative relation, a proposition is viewed as a cause or result of another. Common causative transitions include: "*so, therefore, hence, because, as a result, consequently, for this reason*". Transitions include "*but, yet, however, nevertheless, although, despite*", (ibid).

Halliday and Hasan (1976: 256), in their turn, classify causal markers into five sub-categories that are:

- General causal relation (thus, accordingly).
- Specific causal relation (for this reason, with this intention).
- Reversed causal relations (for, because).
- Conditional relation (in such an event).
- Respective relation (with regard to this).

It can be noted in the above classification that it is rather general as some of these sub-classes can make up of dependent ones.

1.2.3 Temporal

Leech (2006: 17) indicates that temporal is an adverb or adverbial that adds information about the time of the happening described by the rest of the clause, for example: "*now, recently, on Monday, since I saw you last*". The commonest type of time adverbial answers the question 'When?' Two other types of time adverbial are those of *frequency* (answering the question 'How often?') and of *duration* (answering the question 'How long?'):

- Last Friday we went to the park. (time-when)
- The phone bill has to be paid every month. (frequency)
- Why don't you stay with us for a week or two? (duration)

Additionally, Sayidina (2010: 256) illustrates that temporal refers to proposition that can be presented as following or preceding another. Temporal relations also include the organizing of argument in discourse. Typical temporal relationships involve: "*then, next, previously, before, after; first, second; the first point, the second point, the final point*".

Besides, Schiffrin (1987: 240) points out that there are two types of temporal transitional words which are "*now*" and "*then*". "*Now*" is used to refer to "the speaker's progression through a discourse which contains an ordered sequence of subordinate parts" whereas "*then*" points out succession in time between two events.

1.2.4 Adversative

Crystal (2011: 15) states that the term adversative is an aspect or construction which expresses a contraction circumstance. Adversative meaning can be explained in several grammatical ways (as 'adversatives'), such as through a conjunction "but", adverbial "however, nevertheless, yet, in spite of that, on the other hand", or preposition "despite, except, apart from, notwithstanding".

In this regard, Halliday and Hasan (1976: 251) distinguish two types of adversative transitional words which are "internal and external". They are used to describe relationship inherent in the phenomenon of language talks and to the communication processes.

1.3 Data Analysis

In this section, the researcher will analyze four texts that are related to "Wuthering Heights" written by Brontë (1974). It involves transitional words with different types as investigated below. However, Sayidina (2010)'s model will be adopted.

Text (1)

'Sorry? he'll break his heart should anything happen!' I replied. 'Don't alarm him more than necessary.' 'Well, I told him to beware,' said my companion; and he must bide the consequences of neglecting my warning! Hasn't he been intimate with Mr. Heathcliff lately?

Discussion

It can be observed that the current text has a transitional word which is *and*. The type of such transitional word is called additive. It joins the preceded sentence "*I told him to beware*" by the following one "*he must bide the consequences of neglecting my warning!*".

Text (2)

"An awful Sunday," commenced the paragraph beneath. 'I wish my father were back again. Hindley is a detestable substitute—his conduct to Heathcliff is atrocious—H. and I are going to rebel—we took our initiatory step this evening'".

Discussion

The preceding text has transitional words, i.e. *and*, *evening*. The type of these transitional words is called temporal. It is used to add information about the time of the happening.

Text (3)

"Deprived of the advantage of wages: quite unable to right himself, because of his friendlessness, and his ignorance that he has been wronged".

Discussion

As far as the previous text is concerned, it can be noticed that it involves a transitional word, i.e. *because of*. The type of such transitional word is called causative. It is used to match two ideas linking the effect "*quite unable to right himself*" by the reason "*his friendlessness, and his ignorance that he has been wronged!*".

Text (4)

"It was named Catherine; but he never called it the name in full, he had never called the first Catherine short: probably because Heathcliff had a habit of doing so."

Discussion

Two types of transitional words can be distinguished that are: adversative word *but* which expresses an antithetical circumstance where Heathcliff does not call Catherine with her name although he knows it. Furthermore, the current text has also the causative transitional word which is *because*. It links the effect and the reason.

Section Two

Arabic Transitional Words

2.1 Transitional Words: Overview

Ryding (2005: 407) defines transitional words as an element in a text which indicates a linking or transitional relation between "phrases, clauses, sentences, paragraphs" or larger pieces of discourse, exclusive of referential or lexical connections.

Alosh (2005: 273-274) states that transitional words, or connectors, are powerful devices which help students at almost all levels to make cohesive discourse in speaking and writing. These words are used to bind words, phrases, and sentences together while expressing a certain function at the same time, such as contrasting thoughts and expressing reasons.

2.2 Types of Transitional Words

He (ibid) classifies transitional words into six major groups which are as follows:

2.2.1 Additive Items

This connective is of the highest frequency of all transitional words (almost 50% of all Arabic connectives) and occurs at all levels of text to "signal an additive relationship". These additive items are (و، ف، ثم، ايضاً، او، ام، كما، بالاضافة الى، الى جانب، علاوة على، فضلا عن). For example:

ya-tafiiallaq-u bi-qaDaayaa l-fiiraaq-i wa-l-suudaan-i wa-liiyyaawa-l-Suumaal-i wa-l-buusināt-i wa-kashmiir-a wa-l-shiishaan-i.

يتعلق بقضايا العراق والسودان وليبيا والصومال وبوسنة وكشمير والشيشان.

It is concerned with the problems of Iraq, The Sudan, Libya, Somalia, Bosnia, Kashmir, and Chechnia, (ibid: 409).

2.2.2 Contrastive Items

Ryding (2005: 411) adds that these conjunctions indicate contrast in lexical content between two parts of a sentence. For instances: bal (بل) rather; but actually' and 'inna-maa (انما):

lam ta-kun tasjiil-an faqaTwa-√inna-maahuwanfiikaas-un li-l-waaqfi-i l-ijtimaafiyy-i.

لم تكن تسجيلاً فقط وانما هو انعكاس للواقع الاجتماعي

It was not only documentation, but moreover a reflection of social reality.

2.2.3 Causative Items

Alosh (2005: 283) mentions that causative connectors can be introduced justifications or conclusions of the units they match, such as, (بفضل، بسبب، كي، حيث أن، من هنا، نظراً ل). For instance:

احب المشي لانه يساعد على التفكير

I like walking because it helps me to think.

2.2.4 Sequential Items

He (ibid: 284) points out that this type of transitional connectors implies a sequential meaning (coming later in time than the action in the preceding sentence or clause), such as, (اولاً، اخيراً، في الختام). For example:

ختاماً اتوجه بالشكر لكل من ساهم في تنفيذ هذا المشروع

- Finally, I'd like to thank all who contributed to the completion of this project.

2.2.5 Conditional Items

This type of transitional connectors connects the conditional sentence with its response in terms of time sequence, such as, (اذا، وأن). For example:

ستجيدنه في مكتبته اذا اتصلت به بعد العاشرة.

You will find him in his office if you call him at ten, (ibid: 286).

2.2.6 Resultative Items

Ryding (2005: 413) indicates that resultative connectors refer to words such as (اذ، حتى، اذن) that have a resultative meaning. These particles can introduce clauses providing rationales or reasons for the main clauses. For example:

-The ruling republican party realized an overwhelming victory over its opponents since it obtained most of the seats.

Haqqaq-a l-Hizb-u l-jumhuuriyy-u l-Haakim-u naSr-an saaHiq-an fi alaaamunaafis-ii-hi √idhHaSal-a fi alaaamufiZam-i l-maqaafid-i.

ولم نزل في النمو حتى اصبحنا من اهم مدن المنطقة

2.3 Data Analysis

In this section, the researcher will analyze four verses of the Holy Quran. They involve transitional words with various types as investigated below. However, Alosh (2005)'s model will be adopted.

Verse (1)

"لَيْنٌ لَّمْ يَنْتَهُ الْمُنَافِقُونَ وَالَّذِينَ فِي قُلُوبِهِمْ مَرَضٌ" (سورة الاحزاب، 60)

Translation

"Truly, if the Hypocrites, and those in whose hearts is a disease".

Discussion

It can be observed that the present verse has an additive transitional word which is (و) and. The type of such transitional word is used to signal an additive relationship.

Verse (2)

"221" وَلَا تَنْكِحُوا الْمُشْرِكَاتِ حَتَّى يُؤْمِنَنَّ" (سورة البقرة،

Translation

"Do not marry women who associate [others with God] until they believe".

Discussion

The preceding verse has transitional words, i.e. (حتى) until. The type of these transitional words is called conditional.

Verse (3)

262"لَمْ يَلْبِغُوا مَا أَنْفَقُوا مَنْأَ وَلَا أَدَى لَهُمْ أَجْرُهُمْ (سورة البقرة،

Translation

- *And follow not up their gifts with reminders of their generosity or with injury,*

Discussion

In this previous verse, it is observed that it has a sequential transitional words, i.e. (ثم) *then*. The type of such transitional word implies a sequential meaning.

Verse (4)

"وَلَا جُنَاحَ عَلَيْكُمْ إِن كَانَ بِكُمْ أَدَى مِّنْ مَّطَرٍ أَوْ كُنْتُمْ مَّرْضَىٰ أَن تَضَعُوا أَسْلِحَتَكُمْ" (سورة النساء: آية 103)

Translation

"but there is no sin on you if you put away your arms because of the inconvenience of rain or because you are ill".

Discussion

As far as the previous verse is concerned, it can be noticed that it involves two transitional words, i.e. (إن) *means because of* and (إن) *means if*. (إن) *means because of* is called causative which is used to linking the effect by the reason whereas (إن) *means if* is called conditional.

Verses (5)

"مَنْ يُطِيعِ الرَّسُولَ فَقَدْ أَطَاعَ اللَّهَ" (سورة النساء، آية 80)

Translation

"He who obeys the Messenger, obeys Allah"

Discussion

Concerning the current verse, it is observed that it has a resultative transitional words, i.e. (ف) *then*. The type of such transitional word points out a resultative meaning.

Section Three**3.1 Differences and Similarities**

Certain differences and similarities can be observed in both English and Arabic transitional words. Such issues can be mentioned below:

1. In both English and Arabic, transition words are words that are used to link ideas in a logical progression from one to the other. They indicate a linking or transitional relationship between phrases, clauses, sentences, paragraphs or larger units of discourse, exclusive of referential or lexical ties. They are frequently used, in both languages, in writing to make ideas and to indicate important points. In both English and Arabic languages, transitional words are existed which are used to support and connect ideas whether in sentences, paragraphs or texts.

2. In English, there are four types of traditional words can be distinguished. These are:

- Additive is a transitional words which is used to add additional information.
- Causative is a transitional words which is used to link the cause by the effect.
- Temporal is a transitional words which is used to add additional information about the time of the happening.
- Adversative is a transitional words which is used to expresses an antithetical circumstance.

In contrast, Arabic is full of transitional words. Thus, it has various number of such words. However, Alos (2005) classifies them into six types. These are mentioned as follows:

- Additive items are transitional words which are used to add information.
- Contrastive items are transitional words which are used to indicate contrast in semantic content between two parts of a sentence.
- Causative items are used to introduce justifications.
- Sequential items are transitional words which are used to express antithetical circumstances. Expresses an antithetical circumstance
- Conditional items link the conditional sentences with their responses by means of time sequence.
- Resultative items introduce clauses providing rationales or reasons for the main clauses.

To sum up, Arabic shows more illustration than English language. It is obvious through using much more connectors in the verses of the Holy Quran.

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